

COMPRESSIVE TESTING OF FILAMENT-WOUND CYLINDERS

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ABSTRACT

An experimental investigation has been conducted on the compressive buckling and failure of filament-wound circular cylinders. The process of filament winding results in natural fiber undulations within a structure. Experience has shown that the structural performance of full-scale filament-wound shells is significantly lower than that of scaled-down versions used to confirm design adequacy in the laboratory. This investigation identifies one of the relationships between structural performance and scale, as well as some of the causes of reduced structural performance in large-scale structures. It is hypothesized that this effect is related to two conditions: first, the number of fiber tow undulations; and second, the percentage of weak interfaces within the structure. The effect of winding pattern and the resulting location of the fiber undulations were studied by varying the winding parameters. Three types of cylinders were manufactured from Amoco T650-35/1908 graphite/epoxy preimpregnated tow with different winding sequences: $[0/\pm 60]_S$, $[\pm 30/90]_S$, and $[90/\pm 30]_S$. The $[90/\pm 30]_S$ cylinders were manufactured with two different winding patterns (distributed and classical) and radius-to-thickness ratios (15 and 55). All cylinders were loaded in compression to failure. Comparisons of the compressive strength and failure modes demonstrate the relationship between the winding parameters, scale, and structural performance of filament-wound composite cylinders.

KEYWORDS: Filament-winding; Cylindrical Shells; Buckling; Strength; Failure Mechanisms

1. INTRODUCTION

Circular cylindrical shells are a common structural element in the aerospace industry; therefore, it is important to understand the behavior of the shells when loaded, particularly in compression. The stability of cylindrical shells has been covered quite extensively as evidenced by well-written overviews in the literature (1-5). The compressive buckling problem has received more attention than most structural mechanics problems because of the large discrepancy between experimental results and analytical predictions. This discrepancy is primarily due to the imperfection sensitivity of the cylindrical shell when loaded in axial compression. The introduction of composite materials has further complicated this phenomenon as evidenced by studies in the literature, including works by Simitses et al. (6-7) and Booton and Tennyson (8), which address the effects of both geometric and material imperfections.

The structural performance of full-scale filament-wound composites has been shown to be much lower than for smaller scale samples. Cylinders manufactured by filament winding contain natural fiber defects. These defects arise when the fiber tows cross-over one another during an off-axis winding, often referred to as a helical winding path. Helical winding can result in two distinct tow patterns: distributed or classical. Using a computer-controlled filament-winding machine, process parameters can be chosen such that the undulation locations are distributed evenly over the surface of the cylinder (distributed pattern) or the tow undulations can form in distinct circumferential and helical regions (classical pattern). In either case,

weak interfaces exist between the interlaced and/or non-interlaced layers. Previous work has indicated that the number of tow undulations within a helical layer and the percentage of weak interfaces in the laminate directly influence the structural response in compression (9).

This study examined the influence of undulation density and location on the structural response of filament-wound cylinders subjected to axial compression. The undulation locations within a layer are a function of the winding angle, while the percentage and distribution of undulations was dependent on the type of winding pattern employed; i.e., distributed or classical. The location of the undulation through the thickness and the number of weak interfaces are determined by the winding sequence. The experiments were designed to clarify the effect of these internal defects on the buckling and failure mode of filament-wound cylinders.

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Manufacturing of Filament-Wound Cylinders Prior to this study, various winding and curing techniques were investigated to obtain the highest quality filament-wound cylinders. In addition to the tow undulations, several other defects may arise depending on the particular manufacturing techniques employed. These defects are manifest as tow twists, fiber wrinkling, and high void content. The problem of tow twisting during winding was easily resolved by modification of specific pieces of the filament-winder, and by careful programming of COMPOSITRAK, the McClean-Anderson filament-winding software package. However, the wrinkling and void content problems are much more difficult to avoid.

The cylinders were manufactured on a 15 cm (6-inch) diameter by 0.64 cm (2.5-inch) thick steel mandrel, which was coated with Airtech Release-All No. 100. An AMOCO T650-35/1908 Graphite/Epoxy material system was used for all specimens. Each cylinder was wound with five pounds of fiber tension supplied by an American Sahn Model HE-1002A bi-directional tensioner. After winding with the McClean Anderson W-70SP filament winder, the cylinders were over-wrapped with two layers of porous Teflon-coated release fabric and two layers of 3.18 cm (1.25-inch) wide by 0.076 mm (0.003-inch) thick mylar shrink tape. The manufacturer's recommended cure cycle was modified to exclude vacuum and to allow external pressure to be applied by the shrink tape. The temperature was increased 2.2°K (4°F) per min. to 408°K (275°F), held for one hour, increased 2.8°K (5°F) per min. to 450°K (350°F) and held for two hours, then decreased 1.1°K (2°F) per min. to ambient. The temperature was monitored using a thermocouple at the part surface in a computer-controlled Baron autoclave.

2.2 Preparation of Test Specimens In order to ascertain the influence of cross-over patterns on the buckling response, various winding sequences were used to manufacture the cylinders. Circumferential layers were combined with ± 30 degree helical layers, while longitudinal layers were combined with sixty degree helical windings; resulting in $[90_n/\pm 30_n]_s$, (where $n = 1$ or 3), $[0/\pm 60]_s$, and $[\pm 30/90]_s$ stacking sequences. The cross-over patterns are dependent on the different helical angles. By switching the 90° and $\pm 30^\circ$ layers, the effect of stacking sequence was explored. Tripling the cylinder thickness (e.g., $[90_n/\pm 30_n]_s$) also increases the number of weak interfaces, enabling investigation of a scaling parameter. In addition to the classical winding pattern, a distributed pattern was used to manufacture one of the $[90/\pm 30]_s$ cylinders. The variations in winding sequence and helical pattern provided four different cross-over patterns and undulation densities. In the order in which they were tested, cylinders 1 and 2 were $[90/\pm 30]_s$ with classical helical layers, cylinder 3 had a distributed helical pattern, cylinder 4 had a $[\pm 30/90]_s$ stacking sequence with a classical pattern, and cylinders 5 and 6 were $[90_n/\pm 30_n]_s$ and $[0/\pm 60]_s$, respectively, with classical winding patterns.

After fabricating, the cylinders were machined to a length of 24 cm (9.5 inches). This resulted in a gage length of 23 cm (9 inches). Due to the mandrel dimensions, the cylinders had a 15 cm (6-inch) inner diameter. The 6- and 18-ply cylinders had an average thickness of 0.13 cm (0.05 inches) and 0.05 cm (0.2 inches), respectively. In order to ensure that the cylinder ends were flat and perpendicular to the loading direction (the long axis of the cylinder), a special machining

procedure was devised. The cured cylinders were replaced over the processing mandrel with the excess cylinder extending over the end caps. Then the entire assembly was mounted in a lathe. A dremel tool was attached to the lathe tool post, which provided fine adjustments of the machining disk. A composite abrasive cutting blade was used to machine the graphite/epoxy. The lathe and dremel tool were counter-rotated to add stability. The blade was carefully positioned to insure that the ends were flat and a slow feed rate was used to achieve even material removal.

The test cylinders were instrumented with electronic resistance strain gages at various key locations. The first cylinder was fully instrumented with 14 gages, including two 45 degree rosettes. This cylinder was used to verify that the experimental procedure was effective, and that the end plates and alignment fixture provided an axial load. Five locations on the cylinder were instrumented with back-to-back strain gages. The strain gages were placed in this manner in order to determine if local bending occurred. The fully-instrumented cylinder had three gage locations around the circumference at the center of the gage length (120° apart), and two locations one-quarter length above and below the center locations. Data from this cylinder indicated that one pair of back-to back rosettes located at the center would be sufficient for the remaining tests.

Testing was performed on a 267 or 1334 kN (60 or 300 kip) Tinius Olsen axial machine, depending on the cylinder thickness. Special end fixtures were manufactured from standard carbon steel to apply the clamped boundary condition (see Figure 1). Each end plate was machined with a 0.64 cm (0.25 inches) deep groove with a 7.49 cm (2.95 inches) inner radius wide enough to accommodate the thickest cylinder. One end plate was machined with a concentric recessed area which positioned the hemispherical alignment fixture. The alignment fixture helped to insure that the cylinder was subject to a purely axial load. The grooves of the end fixtures were machined such that the bottom was parallel to the loading surfaces. Four holes were drilled in the end plate which accommodated the alignment fixture between the groove and the recess, to permit access of the lead wires for the internal strain gages. The plates were designed to minimize rotation at the cylinder ends. In order to apply a clamping force, molten Cerrobend,[®] a low melting point alloy, was poured into the groove prior to positioning each end of the cylinder into the groove. The Cerrobend,[®] which has a negative coefficient of thermal expansion, was allowed to solidify around the cylinder ends, providing the desired clamped boundary conditions.

FIGURE 1. Photograph of test configuration.

3. ANALYTICAL INVESTIGATION

3.1 Material Properties The effective longitudinal modulus for the quasi-isotropic stacking sequences was calculated using classical lamination theory (CLT). The material properties for the Amoco system, provided in Table 1, yield a calculated modulus of 51.4 GPa (7.45 Msi). The major Poisson's ratio is 0.3. The Tsai-Hill Failure criterion is used in conjunction with CLT to predict the ultimate compressive strength for the lay-ups.

TABLE 1. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Property	Elastic Modulus [GPa]	Allowable Strength [GPa]
Longitudinal Tension	146.7	1.86
Longitudinal Compression	13.1	1.65
Transverse Tension	9.65	0.06
Transverse Compression	9.65	0.14
Shear	5.52	0.08

3.2 **Finite Element Analysis** A minimum buckling stress was obtained with the buckling analysis provided by ANSYS®. A laminated shell element (STIF99) was used to develop a 6 by 12 grid model of one-quarter of the cylinder. Clamped boundary conditions were employed to simulate the end constraints.

3.3 **Closed-Form Approximation** A Donnell type theory for multilayer orthotropic cylinders has been provided by Card (10) to predict the buckling load of filament-wound cylinders. The A, B, and D matrices for each stacking sequence were calculated using CLT. Simple supports are assumed (i.e., v , w , N_x , N_x and M_x equal to zero) similar to classical cylinder buckling theory. In order to satisfy the governing equations, the following displacement functions are assumed:

$$\begin{aligned} u &= \bar{u} \cos \frac{m\pi x}{L} \cos \frac{n\pi}{r} \\ v &= \bar{v} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} \sin \frac{n\pi}{r} \\ w &= \bar{w} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} \cos \frac{n\pi}{r} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where m and n are the longitudinal half and circumferential full waves, respectively, in the buckling pattern; L is the cylinder length; and the barred terms represent the amplitudes of the displacements. Substitution of the buckling displacements into the cylinder equilibrium equations results in the following stability equation:

$$\left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right)^2 \bar{N}_x + \left(\frac{n}{r}\right)^2 \bar{N}_y = C_{33} + \left(\frac{C_{12}C_{23} - C_{13}C_{22}}{C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}^2}\right) C_{13} + \left(\frac{C_{12}C_{13} - C_{11}C_{23}}{C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}^2}\right) C_{23} \quad (2)$$

where \bar{N}_x is the applied stress resultant, \bar{N}_y is 0, and the following definitions are introduced:

$$C_{11} = A_{11} \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right)^2 + A_{66} \left(\frac{n}{r}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

$$C_{12} = (A_{12} + A_{66}) \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right) \left(\frac{n}{r}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$C_{13} = \frac{A_{12}}{r} \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right) + B_{11} \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right)^3 + (B_{12} + 2B_{66}) \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right) \left(\frac{n}{r}\right)^2 \quad (5)$$

$$C_{22} = A_{66} \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right)^2 + A_{22} \left(\frac{n}{r}\right)^2 \quad (6)$$

$$C_{23} = \frac{A_{22}}{r} \left(\frac{n}{r}\right) + B_{22} \left(\frac{n}{r}\right)^3 + (B_{12} + 2B_{66}) \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right) \left(\frac{n}{r}\right)^2 \quad (7)$$

$$C_{33} = \frac{A_{22}}{r^2} + D_{11} \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right)^4 + D_{22} \left(\frac{n}{r}\right)^4 + \frac{2}{r} \left[B_{12} \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right)^2 + B_{22} \left(\frac{n}{r}\right)^2 \right] + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \left(\frac{m\pi}{L}\right) \left(\frac{n}{r}\right)^2 \quad (8)$$

Equation 2 can be used to determine the buckling load when the expression is minimized with respect to integer values of m and n . Similarly, Umera and Kasuya (11) determine the buckling stress for cross-ply and angle-ply laminated cylinders with simply-supported edges and two buckling modes. In this study, the analytical predictions using the relationships developed by both Card (10) and Umera and Kasuya (11) are compared to the results of the finite element analysis and the experimental data.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Failure Mode Each cylinder was loaded in axial compression to catastrophic failure. All of the cylinders failed in the gage section instantaneously with little prior warning, although some audible cracking sounds were emitted at loads greater than 75% of ultimate. Post-failure inspection confirmed that the edges were intact and that neither brooming nor crushing of the ends had occurred. The failure mode reported by Tasi, Feldman, and Stang (12) was quite similar to the modes observed in this study. Tasi et al. tested 15-cm (6-inch) diameter cylinders with a hoop/helical or cross-ply winding sequence. The helical plies used in their study were approximately 2 and 8 degrees. Tasi reported that diamond-shape buckles formed on some of the specimens, similar to those evidenced by post-failure inspections in this study, as seen in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. Photograph of failed cylinder 5.

The first compressive test was performed on a low quality cylinder in order to validate the experimental procedure. Cylinder 1 failed at two circumferential locations with transverse fractures propagating between the bands. The initial failure was triggered by a single local buckle which formed at approximately one-quarter of the cylinder length from the top. The external hoop layers delaminated near the site where the $\pm 30^\circ$ helical fibers fractured.

The second cylinder tested also had a $[90/\pm 30]_s$ lay-up with a classical helical pattern. This specimen failed at the center of the gage area along a circumferential region. The failure was instantaneous with no visual evidence of local buckling; however, there was audible confirmation of fiber breakage and matrix cracking. During fabrication, tow twisting occurred in two areas on the inner surface, exposing the helical layers. The post-failure inspection revealed that the helical fibers had fractured at one of these locations, possibly initiating a premature failure.

Cylinder 3 was similar to both cylinders 1 and 2, except that it contained no defects on the inner surface and employed the distributed helical pattern. Thin regions of tow buckling occurred in the hoop layer on both the inner and outer surfaces of the cylinder. The buckling path travelled circumferentially and diagonally (see Figure 2). A local buckle was visible in the failed deformation, with failure limited to the upper half of the cylinder.

In both cylinders 1 and 3, local buckling was observed in only a single location. This could be due to the alignment fixture, which had freedom to rotate in the circumferential direction. As noted by Tasi et al (12), rotational freedom can relieve stress in the unbuckled portion of the cylinder and result in a fracture-type failure mode. The macro- and micro-buckling

was also noted by Marloff and Raghava (13) who tested a similar $[90/\pm 20]_8$ configuration with 14.6 cm (5.75-inch) diameter by 30.5 cm (12-inch) long cylinders. On the other hand, the failure mode of the $[\pm 30/90]_8$ in this study, cylinder 4, was quite different. Audible indications of failure were much louder and no local buckles were detected. The helical layer fractured along tow boundaries and traversed the upper half of the cylinder. Fracture along fiber undulation regions were not exclusive.

Following the failure modes of the thinner specimens, the 18-ply cylinder exhibited more dramatic tow buckling in the inner hoop layer. Tow delaminations and buckles traveled the length of the cylinder along the helical winding path. The exterior surface showed delamination buckling of the hoop layer, mirroring the path of the interior failure. Beneath the buckled fibers on the inner surface, fractures of the helical layers are visible. Fiber fractures, delaminations and matrix cracking (see Figure 2) were audible for the second half of the loading range. The failure damage to the thin and thick cylinders can be compared by observing Figure 3.

FIGURE 3. Photograph of failed cylinders 4, 5 and 2.

Unlike any of the other tests, the $[0/\pm 60]_8$ cylinder had a clean fracture of the 0° layer in a circumferential path around the cylinder approximately 3 to 5 cm (1 to 2 inches) below the upper boundary. There was considerable popping above 33% of the maximum load, with loud indications of delamination and fracture above 80%. Upon failure, pieces of the outer layer delaminated violently, revealing the helical layers. Post-failure examination of the specimen revealed that the helical layer fractured along one of the circumferential crossover regions. However, because the failure was so catastrophic, the exact failure sequence could not be confirmed.

4.2 Stiffness All of the cylinders were wound with a quasi-isotropic layup; consequently, the orthotropic longitudinal elastic modulus predicted using CLT is the same for all of the cylinders. The principal stresses were calculated on both surfaces with the data obtained from the strain rosettes. Localized bending was accounted for by averaging the back-to-back strains. The applied stress was plotted against the measured principal strain to obtain the local elastic modulus for each cylinder. The experimental and predicted values are compared in Table 2. The experimental moduli compare favorably with data from Foral, Wright, and Humphrey (14) for cylinders with combined hoop and helical windings.

TABLE 2. COMPRESSIVE ELASTIC MODULI

Specimen		Predicted (CLT) [GPa]	Measured [GPa]	Relative Error [%]	Failure Strain [micro-strain]	Relative Bending [%]
1	$[90/\pm 30]_s$ CLASSICAL	51.7	41.4	20	4800	1.3
2	$[90/\pm 30]_s$ CLASSICAL	51.7	46.2	10	5630	32
3	$[90/\pm 30]_s$ DISTRIBUTED	51.7	46.9	9	6070	24
4	$[\pm 30/90]_s$ CLASSICAL	51.7	44.8	13	5220	3.6
5	$[90_3/\pm 30_3]_s$ CLASSICAL	51.7	36.5	29	9200	3.0
6	$[0/\pm 60]_s$ CLASSICAL	51.7	46.2	10	5000	5.2

The experimental modulus for cylinder 1 was much lower than the other specimens. This is attributed to a higher void content and other manufacturing defects. As the first specimen to be manufactured, the processing procedure was not fully refined. The other $[90/\pm 30]_s$ specimens, cylinders 2 and 3, and the $[0/\pm 60]_s$ cylinder had comparable reductions of 10%, 9%, and 10%, respectively. A slightly larger reduction in modulus, 13%, is noted for the cylinder with externally wound helical layers; however this is within the error tolerance of the experimental analysis and further tests are required to draw and conclusive comparisons. Marloff et al (12) reported a 4.4% reduction for their cylinders with 20° helical layers. Card (9), on the other hand, noted that there were greater discrepancies between predictions and experimental values when winding angles exceeded 25° because of matrix nonlinearities. Cylinder 5 had three times as many layers, but approximately four times the thickness. This cylinder also exhibited three times the reduction in longitudinal modulus.

In addition, the ratio of the surface strain and the average mid-plane strain, tabulated in the last column, provides an estimate of the degree of bending and is indicative of the failure mode. The second and third $[90/\pm 30]_s$ cylinders exhibited considerable bending at the gage location. The first cylinder tested with this configuration contained too many defects and failed prematurely, thus little bending was detected. The bending stiffness for the cylinders with $\pm 30^\circ$ and 0° outer layers is much greater therefore only slight bending occurred. The strain to failure is also included in Table 2. It is interesting to note that the failure strain for cylinder 5 is almost twice the other cylinders because it failed in compression not buckling.

4.3 Strength The predicted and measured ultimate failure stresses are summarized in Table 3. The experimental values for the six cylinders are compared to both the finite element predictions, theoretical approximations, and CLT predictions (ultimate compressive failure). The relative error (last column in Table 3) is calculated with respect to the finite element solution for all cases except cylinder 5. The 18-ply cylinder failed in compression rather than buckling; therefore, the failure stress is compared to the CLT prediction. The relative error for the $[90/\pm 30]_s$ cylinders decreased as the processing quality improved. Cylinder 4 came closest to achieving the theoretical predictions, while cylinder 6 had the greatest discrepancy, even though cylinder 1 contained the most defects.

In the study performed by Card (10), experimental failure stresses were 65-80% of the theoretical predictions, depending on the winding angle. The measured values in this study fall within this range, and the performance of cylinders with winding angle greater than 25° exceeds those noted by Card. It should also be noted that, when comparing cylinders of similar processing quality, the cylinder with a circumferentially-wound outer layer failed at a higher stress than the cylinder

with a helical outer layer. Similarly, Card mentioned the improved performance of cylinders with over-wound hoop layers. In a study on laminated graphite-epoxy cylinders (not filament-wound) performed by Kobayashi et al (15), $[0/\pm 60]_s$ cylinders with diameters and lengths of 20 cm (8 inches) failed at 93% of the predicted buckling load. These values are much higher than those obtained for filament-wound cylinders.

TABLE 3. COMPRESSIVE FAILURE STRENGTH RESULTS

Specimen	Compressive Ultimate Stress [GPa] (a)	Predicted Buckling Stress [GPA]		Measured Compressive Failure Stress [GPa] (d)	Relative Error [%] 100*(c-d)/c	
		[GPA]				
		Rayleigh-Ritz Approx. (Simple Supports) (b)	ANSYS Finite Element (Clamped Ends) (c)			
1	$[90/\pm 30]_s$ CLASSICAL	0.51	0.33	0.34	0.20	40.9
2	$[90/\pm 30]_s$ CLASSICAL	0.51	0.41	0.42	0.27	35.7
3	$[90/\pm 30]_s$ DISTRIBUTED	0.51	0.42	0.42	0.29	31.3
4	$[\pm 30/90]_s$ CLASSICAL	0.51	0.43	0.36	0.27	24.8
5	$[90_s/\pm 30_3]_s$ CLASSICAL	0.51	1.56	1.60	0.34	34.6
6	$[0/\pm 60]_s$ CLASSICAL	0.57	0.44	0.40	0.23	41.1

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study has demonstrated that filament-wound composite cylinders loaded in compression are adversely affected by natural fiber defects. Failure is initiated by local buckling near the circumferential cross-overs. External hoop layers delay the onset of buckling and minimize external surface damage, but do not significantly alter the failure mode. Thus, design and manufacturing quality strongly influence the compressive strength. The stiffness is reduced as the number of weak interfaces is increased.

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